

YOLOV10-S FOR 3D PRINTING ANOMALY DETECTION AND CLASSIFICATION

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ABSTRACT

The rapid advancement of additive manufacturing, particularly Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM) 3D printing, has transformed prototyping and small-scale production. However, anomalies such as extrusion problems, spaghetti, stringing, and warping continue to compromise print quality, leading to material waste and inefficiencies. These challenges highlight the need for automated, real-time defect detection systems aligned with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals 9 and 12. This study developed and evaluated a real-time anomaly detection and classification system using the YOLOv10-S model. A dataset of common 3D printing defects, compiled from public repositories, was preprocessed and used to train and validate the model under various image conditions, including RGB and grayscale. Paired T-test revealed significant differences between training and validation losses, indicating localization challenges. One-way MANOVA showed that anomaly type influenced detection performance, with spaghetti achieving the highest accuracy and extrusion problems the lowest. RGB images outperformed grayscale, highlighting the advantage of color features in detection. The final model demonstrated strong and consistent performance across validation and testing, confirming its effectiveness for real-time defect detection in FDM 3D printing.

COMPUTER SCIENCE CONCEPTS

• Neural Networks • Supervised Learning by Classification • Object Detection • Real-time Image Processing

KEYWORDS

3D Printing, Additive Manufacturing, Anomaly Detection, YOLOv10-S, Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM), Object Detection, Computer Vision

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1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, industries have shifted to digital prototyping with the use of computer-aided design (CAD), but many still rely on traditional subtractive manufacturing (SM), which is often inefficient. The advent of additive manufacturing (AM), commonly known as three-dimensional (3D) printing, has changed this field by giving ways to the creation of physical objects from digital designs [1]. In contrast to conventional manufacturing methods, additive manufacturing (AM) operates on the principle of item creation by layer-by-layer stacks of materials [2].

Today, 3D Printing technology is widely used in various fields, particularly in the manufacturing industry, due to the availability of affordable fused-deposition modeling (FDM) 3D Printers, which makes it accessible to most individuals and small-scale businesses [3]. Consideration of the quality and accuracy of the end products becomes a fundamental factor. However, during production, problems such as defects occur, resulting in the rejection of the printed object. This leads to a loss of time and resources and contributes to plastic waste [1].

The sustainable development goals (SDG), established by the United Nations in 2015, integrated 17 specific goals to end poverty, as well as other deprivations, by an urgent call for action in all countries [4]. Among these goals is the need to address problems such as waste in production and unsustainable processes that consequently lead to the environment and resources to be jeopardized. This issue highlights the importance of SDG 9, which promotes resilient and sustainable industrial practices, and SDG 12, which focuses on the area that ensures sustainable consumption and production patterns. By addressing the plastic, time, and resource waste generated by 3D Printing technology, the manufacturing industry aligns with the objectives of the United Nations.

To achieve these goals effectively, this study implements a real-time anomaly detection during 3D Printing. This approach seeks to alleviate the problems and improve production efficiency with the use of minimized rework, reduced operational costs, and enhanced sustainability and protection of the environment with the decrease of the disposal of defective parts. The researchers use machine learning, specifically YOLOv10-S, to create a real-time

assessment of the object during the 3D Printing process. The study also follows a multi-class classification approach, to make it possible to detect and classify the specific types of defects present to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of the remedial measures throughout the 3D Printing process.

1.1 Scope of the Study

This study mainly focuses on examining and identifying the different types of anomalies that occur during the real-time 3D Printing process using Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model, specifically You Only Look Once version 10 (YOLOv10) for anomaly detection and classification. YOLOv10 is one of the recently launched versions of the popular YOLO series that aims at providing fast and accurate object detection when compared to its predecessors as it has better architecture. Among all the different variants of the model, the researchers chose to focus on YOLOv10-S which provides an excellent balance between speed and accuracy.

The researchers train the models using publicly available datasets from Roboflow [5]. Images of defective prints are gathered from various sources to ensure that anomalies are equally represented in the context of the 3D Printing process. The images are also preprocessed to allow for a uniform input size to be fed into the YOLOv10-S model; the image size is therefore kept fixed at 640x640. However, it must be noted that the paper does not establish all possible defects in an FDM printer. Instead, it focuses on the detection of spaghetti, stringing, extrusion problems, and warping anomalies that occur most frequently in 3D Prints and are the only considered anomalies in the available dataset, thus limiting the scope of defect identification and classification to these specific types. Additionally, prints with intentionally induced porosity, spaces, or holes are not included in the training dataset, which leads to incorrect detection of such features as anomalies.

With the presence of various types of 3D Printers, the researchers also decided to focus exclusively on the FDM printer. Despite these limitations, the selected dataset and printer type are sufficient for evaluating the feasibility of applying YOLOv10-S to real-time anomaly detection in FDM-based 3D printing. This technique has been widely used in 3D Printing technology, especially in home-based operations, education, and small businesses, which propels researchers to seek to produce relevant and applicable data for this significant number of users. This approach provides the advantage of a controlled environment, which is fundamental in securing the consistency and reliability of the collected data. Including various 3D Printers complicates the analysis due to the wide range of technologies and behaviors observed across different machines. The results of this study are not necessarily generalizable to other forms of 3D Printing, such as stereolithography (SLA), which uses an ultraviolet (UV) laser to cure liquid resin, or selective laser sintering (SLS), which fuses powdered materials with a laser.

2 METHODOLOGY

To establish smooth-flowing training of the model, the researchers followed a systematic process to ensure reliable model performance. The researchers started with data preparations consisting of organizing the collected dataset, addressing data imbalance using a random under-sampling method, splitting the dataset and allocating a percentage for each phase, and augmenting the dataset to address the hypothesis. After thorough preprocessing to capture key features, the YOLOv10-S model was trained and evaluated using performance metrics such as precision, recall, and mAP50 to assess its accuracy and effectiveness with paired t-test and one-way MANOVA.

2.1 Research Design

The study implemented and utilized an experimental research design to check whether a defect is detected and what type of anomaly is detected in a 3D Printing process. Specifically, the YOLOv10-S was trained to detect defects during the 3D Printing process and classify them. The experimental research design was used in this study as it entails scientific experiments for the researchers to obtain reliable and precise results. The experimental approach comprehensively evaluates and analyzes the effectiveness and accurate performance of YOLOv10-S in anomaly detection classification.

2.2 Dataset

The datasets for training YOLOv10-S were sourced from the reliable dataset repository Roboflow [5]. The datasets were crucial in training the models to yield more accurate and precise detection and classification, which were effectively used in the deployment stage. The datasets used in training the ability to detect and classify anomalies are the following: extrusion problem, spaghetti, stringing, and warping. Table 1 shows the characteristics the collected dataset had to make the model training possible.

Dataset	Anomaly Detection and Classification Dataset
File type	JPG & TXT
Image size for Anomaly Classification	640x640 pixels
Anomaly Classification	Extrusion Problem, Spaghetti, Stringing, and Warping
Original total number of images	6,895

Table 1: Dataset Characteristics

A total of 6,895 images were collected from Roboflow [5]. Specifically, 1,327 images of spaghetti were exported, 1,280 for stringing, 1,744 for under extrusion, 1,345 for over extrusion, and 1,199 for warping. Initially, the dataset contained 1,000 images sourced from Roboflow. However, upon further investigation, it was discovered that several images in the validation and test sets were repeated. To maintain dataset integrity, these duplicates

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were removed, and additional images were sourced from platforms such as Kaggle^[6] and Zenodo^{[7][8]} to expand the dataset. Moreover, the datasets underwent cleaning, which involved deleting .txt files that contained more than five values together with their corresponding image to remove inconsistency. Blurry or extremely poor-quality images found across all data splits were also removed, as they do not represent usable data. After the researchers address the data imbalance and segmentation, the final allocation of images for each classification is shown in Table 2.

Classification	Original Number of Images	Final Number of Images
Spaghetti	1,327	1,000
Stringing	1,280	1,000
Over Extrusion	1,345	1,000
Under Extrusion	1,744	1,000
Warping	1,199	1,000
Total	6,895	5,000

Table 2: Anomaly Detection and Classification Dataset Composition

2.3 Procedures

The dataset was separated into three phases: Training, Validation, and Testing. Each classification was allocated only 1,000 from the original number of images as the data imbalance was addressed. The researchers followed the 80:10:10 ratio for this data splitting. After the data splitting, the dataset then proceeded to the training of the YOLOv10-S model in detecting and classifying 3D Printing anomalies.

During the training phase of the model, 80% of the total dataset for each group was allocated to establish a strong foundation for the models. This phase helped the model to learn the patterns in each image, the relationship between pixels of the image, and the small features within the data. Then, 10% for the validation phase helped filter out the overfitting that happened iteratively during the training phase. Finally, the testing phase, the other 10% of the dataset, was an unbiased procedure for assessing new and completely unseen data.

The researcher applied random under-sampling for each category to address data imbalance. Since the images collected showed similar characteristics and lacked variation for each classification, the researcher combined the over extrusion and under extrusion into one group and reduced the number of images from the overrepresented categories. Upon analyzing the distribution of images, it was observed that combining the two extrusion-related defects, under extrusion and over extrusion, resulted in an imbalance within the dataset. To address this, the researchers applied data augmentation techniques to oversample the minority class and ensure a more balanced representation across all classifications. Specifically, rotation within a range of -10° to $+10^\circ$ and the addition of noise affecting up to 1.5% of the pixels were used to synthetically increase the number of samples in the underrepresented category. As a result of this process, the

final dataset was evenly distributed, allocating 2,400 images for the training set and 300 images each for the validation and test sets per anomaly classification. This strategy led to a substantial final dataset comprising 12,000 total images, ready for model training and evaluation. This final, balanced allocation was critical for preventing model bias and ensuring high generalizability across all defect types. Table 3 represents the final dataset allocation for each anomaly in each phase.

Dataset	Number of Images for Training	Number of Images for Validation	Number of Images for Testing
Extrusion Problem	2400	300	300
Spaghetti	2400	300	300
Stringing	2400	300	300
Warping	2400	300	300

Table 3: Dataset allocation for each phase after augmentation

2.4 Measurement and Statistical Treatment

This section focused on measuring and analyzing the performance of the YOLOv10-S model in detecting and classifying 3D printing anomalies. The evaluation centered on two major aspects: the training and validation loss values, which reflect the learning efficiency of the m, and the accuracy metrics—precision, recall, and mean Average Precision at 50% Intersection over Union (mAP50)—which indicate how well the model identifies and classifies anomalies. Precision, recall, and mAP50 scores were used to quantify the significant difference in the accuracy of detection and classification capabilities of YOLOv10-S. The two statistical tools, Paired T-test and One-Way MANOVA, were used to quantify significant differences in the dependent and independent variables of the study.

The assessment was carried out across different anomaly categories, including extrusion problems, spaghetti, stringing, and warping, as well as between RGB and grayscale image datasets to determine variations in detection accuracy and classification performance. To ensure the statistical validity of the results, a paired t-test was used to identify significant differences between the performance of YOLOv10-S on RGB and grayscale images, while a One-Way Multivariate Analysis of Variance (MANOVA) examined the relationships between the dependent and independent variables across anomaly types.

2.5 Data Preparation

The initial dataset used in this study was primarily obtained from Roboflow^[5]. To maintain dataset integrity, these duplicates were removed, and additional images were sourced from platforms such as Kaggle^[6] and Zenodo^{[7][8]} to expand the dataset. It originally consisted of 6,895 images across five classifications of 3D printing anomalies: spaghetti, stringing, over-extrusion, under-

extrusion, and warping. The images, in .jpg format with corresponding .txt file annotations, were standardized to 640×640 pixels to optimize model training.

During preprocessing, the dataset underwent cleaning to remove duplicate, blurry, and inconsistent annotations, as well as segmentation files containing more than five bounding box values. To address data imbalance, random under-sampling was applied to overrepresented categories, and all classes were equalized to 1,000 images each. Further augmentation, through rotation within $\pm 10^\circ$ and noise addition affecting up to 1.5% of pixels, was implemented to enhance the representativeness of underrepresented classes.

Following preprocessing and augmentation, the dataset was divided into training, validation, and testing subsets following an 80:10:10 ratio. This ensured that 80% of the images were used to train the YOLOv10-S model, 10% for validation during iterative learning, and 10% for final performance evaluation. These preparation steps ensured a balanced, high-quality dataset, enabling the model to effectively detect and classify 3D printing anomalies with improved generalization capability

3 RESULTS

The results obtained from this study were gathered after six separate training sessions of the YOLOv10-S model conducted under two image input modes, RGB and grayscale. Each mode underwent three trials to ensure consistency in performance evaluation. The findings presented in this section focus on the best-performing model from each modality to maintain clarity while providing insights into the ability of the model to detect and classify common FDM 3D printing anomalies, including extrusion problems, spaghetti, stringing, and warping.

The performance of the model was assessed using standard object detection metrics: Precision, which quantifies the model's accuracy in avoiding false positives; Recall, which measures its completeness in finding all true positives; and mean Average Precision at 50% IoU (*mAP50*), which provides a holistic measure of both classification and localization accuracy. These metrics were chosen because they offer a comprehensive, industry-standard evaluation of the object detection capability of the YOLOv10-S architecture.

3.1 Evaluation of YOLOv10-S Training and Validation Losses

To determine the performance of YOLOv10-S, the training and validation losses were statistically compared using paired t-tests. This statistical approach provides quantitative evidence to support observations about the model's learning behavior. For each image type, the evaluation is divided into three key loss metrics: box loss, class loss, and distribution focal loss (DFL loss). This analysis aims to identify which image type and training condition resulted in better loss minimization and generalization, contributing to the selection of the best-performing model.

3.1.1. Box Loss. The box loss measures how well the model localizes objects by predicting bounding box coordinates that align with the ground truth. As shown in Table 4, all six training runs recorded large negative *t*-statistics ranging from -8.91 to -9.38 , with corresponding *p*-values all below 0.05. This consistent statistical difference between the training and validation performance suggests a fundamental limitation in the model's objects localization capacity regardless of the input image modality. Furthermore, the consistently negative *t*-statistics strongly support the observation that the model's performance on unseen data was significantly worse than its performance on the training data. This means that while the model successfully minimized localization error during training, it exhibited slight overfitting when exposed to validation data.

Training Run	t-statistic	p-value
RGB Train 1	-9.09	4.40×10^{-12}
RGB Train 2	-8.91	7.96×10^{-12}
RGB Train 3	-9.09	2.18×10^{-12}
Grayscale Train 1	-9.22	1.37×10^{-12}
Grayscale Train 2	-9.38	1.37×10^{-13}
Grayscale Train 3	-9.17	1.67×10^{-12}

Table 4: T-test for Box Loss

3.1.2. Class Loss. The class loss evaluates how effectively the model classifies detected objects into their correct anomaly categories. As shown in Table 5, only the first RGB training run exhibited a statistically significant difference between training and validation losses ($p = 0.03 < 0.05$). The second RGB run was borderline significant ($p = 0.05$), while the third RGB and all grayscale runs were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). These findings suggest that the classification capability of the model was generally stable, with minimal overfitting across most configurations. The slight significance observed in the RGB runs may indicate that color information introduced additional variability during training, but not to a detrimental extent. Overall, the results demonstrate that YOLOv10-S maintained consistent classification accuracy between training and validation phases, showing its strength in distinguishing between different 3D printing anomalies.

Training Run	t-statistic	p-value
RGB Train 1	1.89	0.03
RGB Train 2	1.65	0.05
RGB Train 3	1.34	0.09
Grayscale Train 1	0.08	0.47
Grayscale Train 2	0.24	0.40
Grayscale Train 3	0.34	0.37

Table 5: T-test for Class Loss

3.1.3. DFL Loss. The distribution focal loss (DFL) focuses on how accurately the model learns the shape and boundaries of detected objects. As shown in Table 6, all six training runs recorded large negative *t*-statistics

ranging from -15.47 to -17.17 , with p-values far below 0.05. These results indicate significant differences between training and validation losses for all configurations. This means that the model performed better in learning object boundaries during training but struggled to maintain the same accuracy when evaluated on validation data. This statistical divergence between the training and validation performance suggests a limitation in the model's object localization capacity regardless of the input image modality.

Training Run	t-statistic	p-value
RGB Train 1	-16.78	2.99×10^{-22}
RGB Train 2	-17.17	1.14×10^{-22}
RGB Train 3	-16.84	2.61×10^{-22}
Grayscale Train 1	-16.33	9.32×10^{-22}
Grayscale Train 2	-15.47	8.68×10^{-21}
Grayscale Train 3	-15.98	2.35×10^{-21}

Table 6: T-test for DFL Loss

3.2 Performance Evaluation of YOLOv10-S Across Anomalies and Color Modes

The detection and classification performance of the model was further evaluated across different anomaly types and color modes. The analysis examined how well the model distinguished among extrusion problems, spaghetti, stringing, and warping using RGB and grayscale images. Multivariate and between-subjects test results were analyzed to determine the significance of anomaly type and color mode on precision, recall, and mAP50. This evaluation provides insight into which anomaly type and color configuration yielded the highest detection accuracy and generalization performance.

3.2.1. Multivariate Analysis. A Multivariate Analysis of Variance (MANOVA) was conducted to examine the effects of anomaly type and color mode on the performance metrics: precision, recall, and mAP50. The multivariate test using Pillai's Trace (Table 7) showed that anomaly type had a statistically significant effect on overall model performance ($p < 0.001$), indicating that the type of printing anomaly greatly influenced the capability of the model to detect and classify. In contrast, color mode showed a moderate multivariate effect on model performance ($p = 0.068$). Although not statistically significant at the 0.05 level, this result suggests that color information contributed moderately to variations in model accuracy across the evaluation metrics.

Effect	Value	F	Sig.	Partial η^2
Anomaly	1.397	4.650	0.000	0.466
Color	0.388	2.965	0.068	0.388

Table 7: Multivariate Test Results (Pillai's Trace)

3.2.2 Between-Subjects Analysis. The between-subjects results were also analyzed to determine how each independent factor, anomaly type and color mode,

individually influenced the detection performance of the model. As shown in Table 8, anomaly type had a strong and statistically significant impact across all evaluation metrics. The results indicated high F-values for precision ($F = 40.67$, $p < 0.001$), recall ($F = 9.35$, $p = 0.001$), and mAP50 ($F = 25.56$, $p < 0.001$), with corresponding large effect sizes (η^2). This suggests that the nature of the defect, such as whether it was a spaghetti, warping, or extrusion problem, greatly affected how accurately the model identified and classified anomalies.

Meanwhile, color mode demonstrated a significant effect only on precision ($F = 9.34$, $p = 0.008$, $\eta^2 = 0.369$), indicating that image color influenced how the model correctly identify true positives. However, its effects on recall and mAP50 were not significant ($p > 0.05$), suggesting that color differences did not substantially affect how well the model captured all instances of anomalies. The Partial Eta Squared values show that Anomaly had a strong effect on the dependent variables (ranging from 0.637 to 0.884), while the effect of Color and the Anomaly \times Color interaction were comparatively smaller. Overall, these findings highlight that anomaly type is a major factor impacting model performance, while color has a limited effect except when interacting with anomaly type for certain metrics.

Source	Dependent Variable	F	Sig.	Partial η^2
Anomaly	Precision	40.67	0.000	0.884
	Recall	9.35	0.001	0.637
	mAP50	25.56	0.000	0.827
Color	Precision	9.34	0.008	0.369
	Recall	1.79	0.200	0.101
	mAP50	3.03	0.101	0.159

Table 8: Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

3.2.3 Estimated Marginal Means. The estimated marginal means analysis revealed clear performance differences among anomaly types and between color modes. As shown in Table 9, Spaghetti anomalies achieved the highest mean values across all metrics, indicating that the model was most effective in detecting this defect type. This was followed by Stringing and Warping, which demonstrated moderate detection performance, while Extrusion Problems consistently yielded the lowest scores, confirming they were the most difficult anomalies to identify accurately. These results suggest that YOLOv10-S was more adept at detecting visually distinct and spatially irregular defects, such as Spaghetti, than subtle irregularities like extrusion inconsistencies.

For color mode, RGB images consistently outperformed grayscale, achieving higher average scores across all three evaluation metrics compared to grayscale. This finding indicates that color information enhanced the ability of the model to distinguish fine visual and texture-based variations among the anomalies.

Category	Type	Precision	Recall	mAP50
Anomaly	Extrusion	51.9	53.0	49.1
	Spaghetti	80.4	73.9	80.2
	Stringing	69.0	61.9	67.1
	Warping	65.3	69.8	65.3
Color	Grayscale	63.8	62.6	63.2
	RGB	69.4	66.6	67.6

Table 9: Estimated Marginal Means (Anomaly and Color)

3.3 Final Model Training Results

The YOLOv10-S model, trained under the RGB Train 1 configuration, shows consistent performance across the validation, and testing phases. During validation, the model achieved a mAP50 of 75.6%, precision of 74.9%, and recall of 70.9%, reflecting strong detection accuracy and balanced classification performance. When evaluated on the test set, the model sustained comparable results, mAP50 of 71.6%, precision of 71.7%, and recall of 73.3%. The close alignment between validation and test metrics indicates that the model effectively generalized to unseen data.

4 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The conclusion of this research paper presents the solutions to the problem statements and discusses potential improvements to the study. This section also provides a summary of the results and an overview of the achievements of the study throughout the experimentation process. The purpose of this section is to provide a comprehensive summary of the research and its findings.

4.1 Conclusion

The research aimed to address two major problem statements related to the YOLOv10-S model. Each subsection presents a summary of the steps completed, results obtained, and conclusions drawn by the researchers. These focus on the performance of the YOLOv10-S model in terms of loss values and its accuracy in detecting and classifying 3D printing anomalies.

4.1.1. Determine the Performance of YOLOv10-S by Evaluating Loss Values. The analysis of YOLOv10-S loss values revealed a significant difference between training and validation, particularly in the Box and Distribution Focal Loss components, which validated the research hypothesis. The results indicated that the model localized defects effectively during training but demonstrated limited generalization in producing accurate bounding box predictions on unseen data. A possible explanation is the complex nature of 3D Printing defects, which often have irregular shapes, unclear edges, or blend into the background, making accurate boundary localization challenging. Additionally, minor variations in lighting, resolution, and filament texture affects how the model

interprets object edges. Since the research hypothesis stated that there is a significant difference between training and validation losses, and the results confirmed this, the hypothesis is accepted. While this implies limitations in the localization capabilities of the model, it does not undermine the effectiveness of the system. This acceptance of the hypothesis directly guides future research efforts toward refining the bounding box regression mechanisms within the YOLO architecture to better handle the visual complexity of FDM anomalies. On the other hand, the stability of classification loss indicates strong generalization in identifying defect types, even when bounding boxes are not perfectly aligned. This finding is significant, as it confirms the reliability of the system in providing accurate, real-time alerts for defect detection in additive manufacturing, supporting its goal of early error detection and quality assurance.

4.1.2 Determine the Accuracy in Terms of Precision, Recall, and mAP50 of YOLOv10-S in Classifying Among the Different Anomalies and Between RGB and Grayscale Images. The YOLOv10-S model exhibited high classification accuracy across all anomaly categories. Spaghetti anomalies obtained the highest precision, recall, and mean Average Precision scores, while extrusion defects recorded the lowest values. The MANOVA results revealed statistically significant effects of both color mode and anomaly type on performance metrics. Estimated marginal means reinforced these findings, particularly highlighting the consistent advantage of RGB and the detectability of Spaghetti anomalies across modalities. The hypothesis that there is a significant effect of anomaly type and color mode on detection performance is therefore accepted. This implies that image modality plays an important role in how reliably different types of anomalies are detected. The variation in effectiveness, such as Grayscale performing better for Warping while RGB excels for others, suggests that a one-size-fits-all model is not optimal. However, for the purpose of building a practical and generalizable detection system, RGB was chosen as the default image setting because it consistently delivered the best performance across the majority of anomalies to balance detection accuracy and implementation simplicity and ensure reliable real-time monitoring.

4.2 Recommendations

Several strategic recommendations are proposed to optimize the application and performance of the YOLOv10-S model in detecting 3D Printing anomalies. These suggestions address key areas for improvement, such as enhancing dataset diversity, fine-tuning model configurations, and expanding the anomaly detection scope to ensure better applicability and reliability.

The performance of the model can be significantly improved by expanding both the dataset and the range of detectable 3D printing anomalies. While the current dataset focuses on common defects such as extrusion, spaghetti, stringing, and warping, future work should incorporate more complex anomalies including thermal inconsistencies, nozzle clogs, dimensional inaccuracies,

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(e.g., F. Andayani, L. B. Theng, M. T. Tsun and C. Chua, "Hybrid LSTM-Transformer Model for Emotion Recognition From Speech Audio Files," in IEEE Access, vol. 10, pp. 36018-36027, 2022, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3163856.)

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layer shifting, layer separation, weak infill, and bonding issues. The addition of a broader variety of materials, printer models, and environmental conditions will improve the capability of the model to generalize, making it more adaptable across diverse production setups. Access to larger and higher-quality datasets will also enable the model to achieve greater detection accuracy and strength, benefiting both novice and professional users.

To enhance accessibility and user interaction, a web-based interface is recommended for the anomaly detection system. This platform would allow users to perform real-time anomaly detection, upload and analyze 3D printing images, and receive automated troubleshooting suggestions based on detected issues. Provision of offline functionality ensures that the system remains operational even in areas with limited internet connectivity, providing reliable support for users in various settings.

Implementation of multiple camera angles around the 3D printer is also recommended to capture a more complete view of the printing process. By minimizing blind spots and providing multiple perspectives, the system can detect complex or hidden defects more effectively. This multi-angle setup enhances detection accuracy, especially for intricate prints where certain anomalies may not be visible from a single viewpoint.

Finally, integrating an automatic stop or pause function directly into the firmware of the printer or control interface would enable the system to take immediate action when anomalies are detected. This real-time intervention can prevent material waste, reduce the likelihood of severe print failures, and promote sustainable production practices. Such automation not only increases printing efficiency and cost-effectiveness but also reinforces the practical value of the system for everyday use in both industrial and research environments.

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